

Democratic innovations in Ukraine: Challenges and pathways forward

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Abstract

This paper explores democratic innovations in Ukraine, examining their development from Ukraine's independence to the present day. Amidst a global "democratic malaise," democratic innovations serve as correctives to representative gaps. As democratic innovations were designed to bridge the gap between citizens and the state, in the situation where elections are not held due to the military situation, these innovations are crucial. The study uses online focus groups conducted with civil society representatives in June 2025 to identify systemic barriers and develop strategies for enhancing their effectiveness. The findings reveal that while Ukraine demonstrates significant "digital resilience," the implementation of these tools faces multifaceted challenges. These include socio-psychological barriers such as "small person syndrome" and Soviet-era paternalism, educational gaps in civic awareness, and institutional limitations like imperfect regulatory framework. Furthermore, the war has introduced infrastructural damage, alongside complex migration dynamics that threaten community cohesion. According to the results of our research, dissatisfaction with the government's performance acts as a motivator for engagement, as citizens use participatory tools to show the authorities how things should be done. The paper concludes by offering strategic recommendations to bridge the gap between participation and tangible results. These include tying innovations to everyday local issues, implementing hybrid online-offline communication models to ensure inclusion, and fostering a "shared language of cooperation" through the education of both youth and civil servants.

Keywords

democratic innovations; Ukraine; trust; civil society organizations; focus group

Introduction

In the face of a global *democratic malaise* characterized by declining trust, lower turnout, and rising cynicism, the search for mechanisms to revitalize representative systems has become an important focus of political science (Newton, 2012). This quest has led to the rise of democratic innovations - processes or institutions designed to revitalize democracy by expanding citizen participation in governance. They aim to strengthen democracy by providing structured opportunities for citizens to engage in deliberation, decision-making, and the exercise of political influence beyond traditional voting. Two main types of democratic innovations are commonly distinguished: deliberative innovations that are intended to foster democratic skills and capacities (citizens' assemblies, citizens' juries, etc.) and direct innovations aimed at empowering citizens by enhancing their autonomy and their ability to initiate political decisions (e.g., participatory budgeting, citizen-initiated referendums, petitions) (Smith, 2009; Gonthier et al., 2024; Tisserand et al., 2025).

Democratic innovations serve as a "corrective" to the perceived failures of representative democracy by providing "lay" citizens with direct agency in governance, thereby fostering a sense of external political efficacy (Addeo et al., 2025). By allowing citizens to determine local budget priorities or participate in deliberative assemblies, these tools bridge the gap between the governing and the governed, reinforcing the legitimacy of the state through transparent and inclusive performance.

The study of democratic innovations is significant due to their potential to mitigate the crisis of political trust. As noted in the TRUEDEM project reports, institutional trust is a prerequisite for a functioning democracy, yet it has remained historically low across many European nations, particularly in Central and Eastern Europe (Gonthier et al., 2024; Krašovec et al., 2025). Political trust has long been regarded as an important element of regime support and factor of the regime stability (Easton, 1975). Political trust drives citizens' interest and engagement in politics, increases voting turnout and makes law-abiding behavior more common (Putnam et al., 1993).

Recent studies of political trust say that for a healthy democracy, the goal should not be "blind trust," but rather well-placed trust - which occurs only when the level of trust expressed by the "principal" (the citizen) matches the actual "trustworthiness" of the agent (Norris, 2022). Democratic Innovations act as "monitoring mechanisms" that provide citizens with the information needed to judge the trustworthiness of their leaders. When these innovations function well, they encourage skeptical trust - a healthy democratic state where citizens trust because the institution has proven its competence and integrity, rather than trusting out of habit or ignorance (Norris, 2022). Meanwhile democratic innovations are not a panacea, suggesting that their success depends heavily on institutional design and context (Newton, 2012).

Ukraine is an interesting case of a country being in crisis to study democratic innovations. In the context of Ukraine, a country currently navigating the dual challenges of post-communist democratic consolidation and a full-scale defensive war, these innovations - ranging from participatory budgeting and electronic petitions to the pioneering citizens' Assemblies and the E-government ecosystem "Diia" - are no longer merely experimental; they are essential pillars of national resilience. As democratic innovations were designed to bridge the gap between citizens and the state, in the situation where elections are not held, these innovations are crucial. Besides, during wartime, the state's ability to maintain democratic continuity is under extreme pressure; yet, Ukraine has demonstrated remarkable "digital resilience" through the Diia platform, which has transformed from a service-delivery tool into a vital e-democracy hub for polls and civil engagement (Global Government Technology Centre in Kyiv, 2025).

Furthermore, the successful implementation of Ukraine's first Citizens' Assemblies in 2024 (Zvyahel and Slavutych) under wartime conditions proves that deliberative democracy can thrive even when traditional electoral cycles are paused due to security concerns (Council of Europe Office in Ukraine, 2025). Studying these innovations in a wartime context is crucial for understanding how participation can prevent authoritarian backsliding and how "participatory resilience" can serve as a foundation for post-war reconstruction and European integration.

The aim of this article is to present an overview of democratic innovations in Ukraine and recommendations on improvement of their effectiveness. For making an overview we chose such democratic innovations such as referendums, participatory budgeting, citizen's assemblies, electronic petitions, and Diia. We chose to analyze the first three as examples of different families of democratic innovations: mini-public (we took citizens' assemblies as an example), participatory budgeting, and referendums (Gonthier et al., 2024). We decided to examine electronic petitions because they gained much popularity after the full-scale invasion. For our consideration, we also took Diia because this is a unique Ukrainian innovation allowing interaction between the government and citizens. It is a comprehensive "state in a smartphone" platform for over 100 public services for individuals and businesses, and access to digital documents (Digital State UA, 2025).

The literature review showed that the topic of legal regulation improvements based on law perspective is covered well (Ромців & Харченко, 2024; Гудзь, 2022). But at the same time other aspects stay hidden. To develop comprehensive recommendations for the improvement of democratic innovation's effectiveness it is reasonable to address representatives of civil society organizations that are closely related to implementation of democratic innovations in Ukraine and familiar with the mechanisms of citizen's engagement.

Our research questions are the following: 1) How to effectively organize innovative forms of citizen participation in Ukraine? 2) How to practically facilitate participation in Ukraine? 3) Are there limitations to implementing democratic innovations in Ukraine?

Democratic innovations in Ukraine

The democratic trajectory of Ukraine since its independence in 1991 provides a good example for examining the mechanisms of institutional resilience and the emergence of participatory governance in a transitional post-Soviet state. Unlike its neighbors, who often followed a more linear path toward authoritarian direction, Ukraine's development has been characterized by a persistent tension between an entrenched patrimonial political system and an increasingly sophisticated, digitally-enabled civil society (Kutsenko, 2025). The period from 1991 to 2022 laid the foundation for these innovations, while the era following the full-scale invasion of 2022 shifted the focus from mechanisms aimed solely at increasing citizen participation in decision-making (Ткачук, 2019) to tools for the existential survival of the nation (Khodan & Burtnyak, 2025). The 2022 invasion acted as a catalyst for "democratic resilience," galvanizing civil society and transforming pre-war innovations into survival mechanisms (Kutsenko, 2025).

The 1991 and 2000 referendums

The initial phase of democratic development (1991–2004) was marked by a profound economic crisis and the rise of oligarchic tendencies and corruption, yet it simultaneously saw the introduction of foundational direct-democracy tools. The 1991 referendum, in which Ukrainians overwhelmingly approved independence, served as the primary act of popular sovereignty that validated the state's existence (IDEA, 2022). The referendum was governed by the Law of Ukraine "On All-Ukrainian and

Local Referendums" (1991) that has since been superseded by the 2021 legislation (Law of Ukraine On the All-Ukrainian Referendum, 2021). This national-level referendum was initiated by the Parliament of Ukraine to provide democratic legitimacy to the Act of Declaration of Independence adopted on August 24, 1991. Held on December 1, 1991, the referendum saw a significant voter turnout of 84.1%. The result provided an unequivocal mandate for sovereignty, with 92.3% of participants (approximately 28.8 million citizens) voting in favor of independence. The referendum stands as the foundational act of modern Ukrainian statehood, successfully translating a legislative declaration into a legally binding reality.

The 2000 referendum was also conducted under the Law of Ukraine "On All-Ukrainian and Local Referendums" (1991). This was a top-down initiative prompted by the President Leonid Kuchma rather than a grassroots citizen movement. The referendum sought public opinion on the reform of the public administration system with four questions related to: restrictions of parliamentary immunity; establishment of additional grounds for dissolution of the Verkhovna Rada by the President of Ukraine; reduction of the number of deputies from 450 to 300. Despite receiving overwhelming public support (ranging from 81.7% to 89.9% affirmative votes), the results were never codified into law. The primary controversy stems from a legal-constitutional mismatch: while the 1991 law was in force during the vote, many of its provisions had become inconsistent with the 1996 Constitution of Ukraine, leading to a failure in implementation.

Participatory budgeting (emerged in 2015)

The 2014 Revolution of Dignity (Euromaidan) acted as a pivotal catalyst, shifting Ukraine from a period of democratic backsliding under President Viktor Yanukovich to European integration being a driving force for institutional reforms.

Participatory budgeting in Ukraine emerged in 2015 as a corollary to the 2014 decentralization reforms. It relies on indirect regulation through such regulatory and legal acts as: Law of Ukraine "On Local Self-Government in Ukraine" (1997, last edited in 2025) (Law of Ukraine On Local Self-Government in Ukraine, 1997), Order of the Ministry of Finance "On Approving Methodological Recommendations on the Mechanisms of Public Participation in the Budget Process at the Local Level" (2020) (Order of the Ministry of Finance On Approving Methodological Recommendations on the Mechanisms of Public Participation in the Budget Process at the Local Level, 2020), Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers "On Ensuring Public Participation in the Formation and Implementation state policy" (2010, last edited in 2025) (Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers "On Ensuring Public Participation in the Formation and Implementation state policy", 2010). Participatory Budgeting mechanism follows a rigorous multi-stage cycle, including project submission by residents, examination, community-wide voting (often via the e-dem.ua platform), and monitoring of implementation. Initially launched in cities like Chernihiv, Cherkasy, and Poltava, the tool's application has become inconsistent due to the security challenges and fiscal constraints imposed by martial law.

The full-scale invasion has deeply influenced the public budgeting process. Participatory budgeting, which had almost stopped in 2022, began to re-emerge as a tool for community engagement under crisis conditions with expenditures redirected toward defense-related ones (Khodan & Burtnyak, 2025).

Electronic petitions (emerged in 2015)

The introduction of electronic petitions in 2015 was intended to give citizens a platform to challenge state decisions and express their will regardless of location (Luchenko, 2019). Governed by the Law of

Ukraine "On Citizens' Appeals," originally adopted in 1996 and most recently amended in 2023 (Law of Ukraine On Citizens' Appeals, 1996). This mechanism operates at both the national and local levels. It is characterized as a citizen-led initiative, representing the most prevalent tool for public participation in the country. Since 2015, electronic petitions have allowed citizens to submit individual or collective appeals to various branches of government, including the President, the Verkhovna Rada (Parliament), the Cabinet of Ministers, and local self-government bodies. For national-level petitions (Presidential, Parliamentary, or Ministerial), a threshold of 25,000 signatures must be reached within a three-month window to trigger official consideration. For local petitions, thresholds and timelines are determined by specific territorial community charters.

However, scientific findings indicate that this institution largely became a "fiction" over time. The primary barrier was the "formal response" mechanism, where officials provided acknowledgments without legal obligations to resolve the underlying issues. This led to a sharp decrease in interest as citizens realized that most registered petitions do not reach a meaningful result (Luchenko, 2019). Although electronic petitions create a political, rather than legal, obligation for authorities to respond, they remain a valuable means of expressing public opinion and highlighting pressing social and economic issues. However, their effectiveness depends on the existence of mechanisms for implementation and responsible responses from officials (Reshota et al., 2021).

After the full-scale invasion in February 2022, electronic petitions to the President of Ukraine have become more popular. Most often, citizens raised the issue of leaving men of military age abroad, awarding the title of Hero of Ukraine, as well as a ban on serving summonses in public places. In 2023, the topics of petitions changed significantly: appeals related to the state's defense capability prevailed - in particular, regarding the awarding of military personnel, the production of FPV drones, demobilization and possible mobilization of deputies.

In general, there are not many examples where an electronic petition has influenced the adoption of a certain political decision. At the same time, successful cases - opening a register of e-declarations, restricting military access to online casinos, and protecting the work of independent online medicine aggregators - show that petitions can mobilize a significant number of citizens around important issues and force authorities to respond promptly (Лушагіна & Лаптіп, 2025).

E-government system Diia and public opinion surveys that appeared within it in 2022

In 2019, the Ministry of Digital Transformation was created to implement a "state in a smartphone" vision. Diia is a mobile app, a web portal and a brand of e-governance in Ukraine designed by this Ministry and issued in 2020 (Єдиний портал державних послуг Дія, 2026). Diia is a Ukrainian brand that combines a mobile application with access to citizens' digital documents, and a single portal of public services for the population and business. There are 23 million users of the Diia by now and over 70 government services are available online. (Єдиний портал державних послуг Дія, 2026). The mobile application Diia allows Ukrainians to access different digital documents (ID card, foreign biometric passport, student card, driver's license, vehicle registration certificate, vehicle insurance policy, tax number, birth certificate, IDP certificate) and services. All digital documents in Diia now have the same legal force as their plastic or paper counterparts. Using the Diia app, Ukrainians can also share digital copies of the documents and pay debts or fines.

Public surveys through the Diia began to work in 2022. Such polls are not equivalent to referendums or elections and have only an advisory nature. According to the government's resolution, polls in Diia will concern "initiatives aimed at solving issues of public administration in various spheres of public life." Regulated by the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine "On the approval of

the Procedure for conducting a survey on initiatives aimed at solving issues of public administration in various spheres of public life, on the Unified State Web Portal of Electronic Services” (2022) (Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine “On approval of the Procedure for conducting a survey on initiatives aimed at resolving public administration issues in various spheres of public life on the Unified State Web Portal of Electronic Services”, 2022). Such surveys can be initiated by the Ministry of Digital Transformation or another executive authority that has submitted a request to the department. These surveys are advisory rather than binding, yet they possess significant political weight. Citizens of Ukraine over the age of 14 will be able to take part in the survey in Diia. At the same time, surveys can be displayed only for certain categories of the population. Some categories of population cannot use Diia – for instance, people who lack knowledge and digital skills, low-income citizens that cannot afford a smartphone and high-quality internet (Marysyuk et al., 2021).

We can give two different examples of whether the results of the Diia polls were translated into actual bills passed by the Parliament and the President (the President can veto a law). The first example refers to May 2022 when Diia organized the voting on the whether Ukrainians should own weapons. The survey was initiated by the Minister of Internal Affairs of Ukraine. Almost 59% of respondents voted to allow weapons for personal protection (a total number of citizens participated in the survey was 1,726,452) (Сітнікова, 2022). On February 23, 2022, members of Parliament supported in the first reading a Project of the Law No. 5708, which provides for the right to civilian firearms. Till now the Law was not adopted, thus there is no permit to carry civilian firearms in Ukraine. The second example refers to December 2022 when a survey on the date for Christmas celebration was launched in the application. A total number of citizens participated in the survey was 1,531,253 (Міністерство культури та інформаційної політики України, 2022). The majority (59%) supported December 25th, leading to a change in the dates of Christmas celebration from January 7 to December 25 enshrined at the legislative level in 2023.

Under the war conditions, the Diia app got new services that include financial support for internally displaced persons, military bond purchases, damaged property compensation claims, and a system for reporting enemy movements, which enabled verified citizens to submit geolocation data on Russian military activities. Also, Diia is considered to be the first-ever fully digital marriage registration service available through the app (Mamedieva, 2025).

Citizens’ assemblies (emerged in 2024)

The most recent development in Ukrainian deliberative democracy is the introduction of Citizens’ Assemblies in 2024. While no dedicated legislation exists for this mechanism, it is indirectly grounded in the Law of Ukraine “On Local Self-Government” (1997, last edited in 2025) (Law of Ukraine On Local Self-Government, 1997), the Law “On Citizens’ Appeals” (1996, last edited in 2023) (Law of Ukraine On Citizens’ Appeals, 1996), and Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine “On Ensuring Public Participation in the Formation and Implementation of State Policy” (2010, last edited in 2025). These Assemblies represent a landmark achievement as the first instances of such a deliberative tool being utilized within a country under war conditions.

Following the methodology developed in collaboration with Council of Europe international expert Eva Bordos, who designed and coordinated the first Citizens' Assemblies in Hungary, 4,000 invitation letters were sent to randomly selected households in each community. The sortition was conducted to accurately reflect, as closely as possible, the population of the community aged 18 and over in terms of age group, gender, educational attainment, and district. The random selection of 45 members (2 places were reserved for internally displaced persons) and 12 substitute members was

conducted using the open-source software, Panelot. To ensure the involvement of as wide a range of residents as possible in the process, including the members of the diaspora, the municipality's website also provided a platform where any resident could submit their suggestions and opinions on the topic (Council of Europe Office in Ukraine, 2024).

Citizens' Assemblies were held at the local level, the Zvyahel community held an assembly in October 2024 regarding the topic "Creating Urban Spaces as Public Locations for Social Interaction and Recovery", while the Slavutych community addressed the topic: "How can we improve the household waste management system in our community?" As of summer 2025, in Zvyahel the city park was improved and work on improving the embankment has begun. In Slavutych local recommendations are planned to be implemented when regional strategy on waste management will be approved (Бахамент, 2025). Both Assemblies were organized by City Councils with expert, methodological and financial support from the Council of Europe project «Strengthening democratic resilience through civic participation during the war and in the post-war context in Ukraine» (Council of Europe Office in Ukraine, 2025).

To summarize the overview of democratic innovations listed above, it can be said that, despite the war, these innovations are being implemented in the country. However, their implementation faces numerous barriers. For instance, results of the second All-Ukrainian Referendum (2000) were never codified into law due to legal contradictions. Local recommendations developed after Slavutych Citizens' Assembly are not implemented yet because the regional strategy on waste management is not approved. Electronic petitions were initially met with enthusiasm, but the instrument has largely lost its popularity. The primary barrier is the "formal response" mechanism: officials provide polite acknowledgments without any legal obligation to resolve the underlying grievances. Consequently, citizens have realized that most petitions fail to reach a meaningful result, leading to a sharp decrease in interest. Very few examples exist where a petition has influenced a significant political decision. To study the barriers deeper and develop measures to eliminate them, we conducted a study that involved experts on democratic innovations in Ukraine.

Research methodology

Initially we planned to organize an onsite workshop using the World Café method to facilitate deliberative engagement and the synthesis of collective intelligence through structured, multi-round dialogue. About 9-12 participants were supposed to be representatives of civil society organizations and trade unions. (Novak et al., 2025). Given the security situation in Ukraine as a whole and in the city of Kharkiv in particular, we decided to use an online focus group (FG) instead. The refusal to hold the event in person was motivated by safety considerations and the research team's desire to involve participants from different regions of the country. Offline participation of individuals from various parts of Ukraine would have required additional time commitments from participants and posed security risks associated with travel.

Conducting a World Café workshop online would also have been technically challenging. This format requires the full involvement of the entire research team throughout the duration of the workshop. If any power or internet issues were to arise, there would be no available backup to replace those experiencing technical difficulties. The city of Kharkiv, where the research team is based, is located quite close to the front line and suffers near-daily attacks. Therefore, the likelihood of disruptions to electricity and internet connectivity is high.

To conduct the online focus group, we developed a discussion guide based on the questions originally intended for the workshop. The focus group was conducted on June 26, 2025. Eight CSO representatives took part in the focus group discussion.

Table 1. CSO representatives focus group participants.

ID	Gender	Age group	Organization role	Organization type	Organization level
P1	M	36-55	Board member	NGO	Local
P2	F	Under 36	Project manager	NGO	National
P3	F	36-55	Chair of the board	NGO	Regional
P4	F	36-55	Head of educational programs	Charity	National
P5	F	36-55	Educational programs coordinator	Civic association	National
P6	F	36-55	Online event coordinator	NGO	National
P7	F	36-55	Community center coordinator	Humanitarian	National
P8	F	36-55	Chair of the board	NGO	National

Before the focus group began, all participants were familiarized with the project information sheet about the TRUEDEM project. They completed a Google Form in which they indicated the organization they represent, the responsibilities they perform within it, and provided information about their gender and age as well as contact details. Prior to the start of the focus group, all participants received a consent form via email, which they signed and returned to us in electronic format. In the sections below, we will present the results of the focus group in accordance with our research questions.

Effective organization of innovative forms of citizen participation in Ukraine

The effective organization of innovative forms of citizen participation, such as participatory budgeting, citizens' assemblies, e-petitions, and referendums, requires a comprehensive approach. This includes civic education, an appropriate legal framework, government support, strong communication, and the inclusion of diverse citizen groups.

Civic education and awareness-raising. FG participants emphasized the need to educate citizens on how participatory mechanisms function, what rights they have, and how to influence decisions. Education should go beyond theory, using interactive methods like simulations, role-plays, and student self-government to help people "try on" the role of an active citizen. These experiences sow seeds of trust and engagement that later grow into meaningful participation.

It is very important to show young people that they can have an impact. This means promoting initiatives such as the creation of youth councils, as well as providing training for young people and active members of these councils, who will be prepared to act (P4).

Very often it is necessary to work with representatives of the authorities as well.

They also need to be trained and reminded that such cooperation is in their own interest (P2).

Legal framework. The existence of statutes and regulations governing participatory tools (e.g. participatory budgets or e-petitions) ensures protected and sustainable participation. From January 1, 2027, adopting local community statutes will be mandatory, offering a chance to embed participation as a norm. A referendum in Ukraine is possible only at the national level, because there is a Law of

Ukraine “On a National Referendum”, but there is still no law on a local referendum. Before the start of the full-scale invasion, a draft law on a local referendum was developed, but it was not adopted.

It is, after all, a regulatory and legal framework — if not at the national level, then at least at the local one. When citizens themselves contribute to the adoption of various regulations, such as those on electronic petitions or participatory budgeting, they continue along this path, having something to rely on and, to some extent, being protected (P1).

Partnership with local authorities. No participatory mechanism can succeed without at least minimal cooperation with local authorities. It is crucial to find allies among local officials who can support initiatives and ensure implementation of decisions. It is important not to oppose the authorities, but to look for partners within the system. An effective practice is for civic associations to meet with officials to establish personal connections, discuss issues together, and prepare advocacy campaigns. FG participants noted that it is necessary not only to educate citizens about the possibilities for their civic participation, but also to train local government representatives to cooperate with civil society representatives.

It still depends on the voluntary consent of the authorities. When we introduce a participatory tool, we cannot be in complete opposition to the government. We need to find those who will support us and gradually expand this circle — whether they are deputies, department heads, or deputy officials. Sooner or later, someone has to become inspired by the idea and become our partner in this process, because the implementation of decisions is extremely important (P1)

Communication and feedback. Effective communication greatly shapes trust in participation as a means of influencing government. It is vital to inform the public about the outcomes of their involvement — which public proposals were considered and implemented. This fosters trust in participation as a meaningful tool rather than a formality. Conversely, simulated participation without real impact undermines credibility. Continuity also matters — successful practices should survive changes in political leadership.

[It is important] to communicate about these decisions — to show where we involved people and what results we achieved. This is the responsibility of those who promote such initiatives, whether it is the civil society sector, specific NGOs, individual activists, or representatives of the authorities. It is essential to talk about these intermediate successes (P1).

Equality and inclusion. Participation must be voluntary, equal, and free from discrimination based on age, education, economic status, or experience. Special attention should be paid to engaging often-overlooked groups — elderly people, youth, people with disabilities, women, and newcomers to civic activity. Involving newcomers poses a unique challenge. For example, the Citizens’ Assembly in Zviahel (on the topic of urban public spaces as sites of social interaction and recovery) used random selection to bring in people who had previously only voted in elections. Lacking expertise in public space design, participants were supported with expert lectures and inclusive discussions featuring people with diverse needs.

Of course, it is also clear that certain national communities — people of different ethnic backgrounds living in Ukraine, such as Roma communities — often remain excluded from the decision-making process, with no one really considering their needs or perspectives (P7).

It is also important to engage different categories of people — we are talking about persons with disabilities, internally displaced persons, veterans, and military personnel. Because my experience shows that their vulnerability actually motivates their civic activity. After going through such difficult life experiences, they often develop a strong desire to participate (P3).

In **addition** to the above points that contribute to the effective organization of innovative forms of civic participation, the participants in the discussions also mentioned **external support** for such forms. In their opinion, it is worth involving reliable external organizations in the facilitation and moderation of processes, which contributes to the formation of trust in the process. As an example, the involvement of external facilitators for the first Public Assemblies in Ukraine (Zvyagel and Slavutych, 2024) is given.

Practical facilitation participation in Ukraine

Participants of the focus group highlighted several key **barriers** that hinder citizen involvement in political decision-making.

Psychological barriers: Many citizens believe their voice doesn't matter ("small person syndrome") or adopt a paternalistic mindset, expecting the state to solve all issues.

I think we need to work on overcoming the "small person" barrier, because every individual can influence what happens in their community. People should shift their mindset toward understanding that everything depends on them — *I am that important person who can make a difference*: to ensure the pothole is fixed, the lights are on, and the bus stops where it's needed. It's also important to work on motivation — to help people realize that the main figure in the state is each of us, this so-called "ordinary" person, not just the mayor, the president, or other officials (P6).

I would probably not call it the "small person" barrier, but rather a legacy of the Soviet past — a kind of paternalism, the belief that someone else will make decisions for you. This is especially true for older people, in my experience, because it seems to me that young people are more actively engaged. But it is extremely difficult to convince the older generation — they still tend to expect that someone will come and solve everything for them (P8).

Lack of awareness: People are often unaware of available participatory mechanisms or do not understand how they work.

The older generation tends to be passive in civic life. At the same time, they are the most disciplined voters — people aged 60 and over participate in elections the most. However, they are generally unaware of other forms of civic engagement. They simply know that they should come and vote when elections are held (P3).

Digital divide: Limited digital literacy, lack of internet access, or specific needs (e.g., visual impairments) prevent participation in online formats.

It's also important to consider which formats to engage with and not to move entirely to an electronic online service... when there's this overwhelming shift to online formats, we often end up discriminating against those who don't necessarily ignore it but rather have lower digital literacy. Those who, in principle, don't trust electronic calculations or don't want to share their personal data openly (P1).

Imitation of participation: Involving formal representatives instead of real community voices discredits the process itself.

I once attended a public hearing at the XXX city council, and it was just awful, you know? There was no real public interest. The authorities brought in what I call “public crazies” — well, the “public crazies” showed up, just shouting, not even listening to what the local government representatives were saying. Then there were the loyal civic activists who voted like in the old Communist Party times — everyone in favor, everyone satisfied. So, what’s the point of such public hearings then? They’re supposed to raise an issue, discuss it, find some compromise solutions, and really ask the public what they think about this or that decision (P3).

Distrust of government: Deeply rooted in society distrust stemming from historical experiences of repression, indifference, or abuse. People believe that participation in government is often associated with corruption or “dirty business.” At the same time, FG participants noted that dissatisfaction with the government's performance could encourage citizens to participate.

In fact, I’ve noticed that it’s precisely the lack of trust in what the authorities are doing that often motivates people. For example, in XXX recently, a public toilet was installed in the city center, and most of the posts about it were saying that the people who made the decision had no sense of spatial planning or urbanistic knowledge — so people said, “let’s help them.” A petition was registered and promoted accordingly. It was all about showing the authorities how things *should* be done because “they’re doing it wrong.” So, this distrust actually turned out to be a very positive example (P1).

Fear and personal risk: In small communities, expressing one’s opinion is often associated with the risk of condemnation or conflict.

But there’s another important point to consider — it really depends on the size of the community. If there are only about a thousand residents, where everyone knows each other — Ivan, Maria, and the rest — then personal relationships play a big role. It’s like, “Look, look, he’s against him,” and as soon as someone says something, they’re immediately seen as taking sides. That’s one thing. Another is that people react differently to criticism. In a big city, when someone registers a petition, it’s not so easy for the neighbors to identify them, so they can do it more freely (P1).

Loss of motivation: Citizens become discouraged when efforts do not bring results.

There isn’t even a tradition of us making collective decisions — that tradition has been largely broken. And as for national referendums, there have only been two: in 1991 and in 2000. Even the 2000 referendum is still debated among scholars — what kind of referendum it actually was — since none of the decisions made during it were ever implemented or put into practice (P3).

Ways to Enhance Citizen Participation:

Education and civic awareness. Promoting knowledge through training, participatory schools, and practical formats like student self-government helps people understand their capacity for influence. Especially important for youth is teaching them that their voice matters not only in school, but also in community life. Sharing success stories motivates others to participate. Civil society organizations (CSOs) should include in their activities advocacy campaigns aimed at changing negative perceptions and encouraging engagement, taking responsibility for tailored messaging that explains why participation matters for individuals. CSOs themselves require support to build active civil society.

Communication and accessibility. Information should be disseminated via multiple channels (social media, printed newsletters, phone calls, in-person meetings). Communication strategies must

consider people's routines. Combining online and offline tools ensures broader outreach, especially to vulnerable groups (people with disabilities, IDPs, veterans, minorities, youth). Participation procedures should be simplified and free of bureaucratic complexity.

Tying participation to everyday life. Engagement should be linked to solving tangible local problems — transportation, lighting, urban planning, and services. Personal relevance increases willingness to participate.

Transparency and results. Demonstrating impact is key: “The petition was supported — the issue was resolved.” Citizen participation is often limited to collecting signatures on a petition, without further support. Initiators lose motivation after achieving a formal result, and there is no monitoring of the implementation of decisions. It is worth involving citizens in monitoring the implementation of decisions, because real participation also includes control, reviewing responses, and tracking the actions of the authorities.

Limitations to Implementing Democratic Innovations in Ukraine

War and instability as the key context. Martial law restricts elections, referendums, and criticism, creating barriers to participation — but not halting it. Despite the war, democratic tools like petitions, public hearings, and initiatives continue to function in Ukraine. However, war has significantly damaged public infrastructure (schools, administrative buildings), particularly in frontline areas, which complicates the implementation of traditional participatory formats.

Thematic and procedural restrictions. The Ukrainian Constitution prohibits referendums on issues such as taxes, the state budget, and amnesty. The Law of Ukraine “On a National Referendum” supplements this list: everything related to matters on law enforcement, prosecution, or courts cannot be put to a referendum. According to focus group participants, overly polarizing or technically complex topics should not be delegated to citizens without proper preparation.

Risks of distrust and vulnerability. Public distrust of authorities — rooted in historical oppression and real examples of non-transparency — can discourage civic engagement. In addition to distrust of the government as such, there may also be distrust of civic participation as a tool for influencing the government may itself be distrusted when it is seen as symbolic rather than effective. A significant obstacle to citizen involvement in activism can be persecution, pressure, even murder (for example, the case of Demyan Hanul in Odessa). This problem can be especially relevant in a small settlement, where it is difficult to maintain anonymity. Insufficient protection of activists can deter citizens from active participation.

The specifics of participation in migration conditions. Due to the war, many Ukrainians are abroad. In this context, the issue of involving people who are temporarily outside the country in participation arises. Online involvement of citizens who have left helps to maintain their connection with the community. At the same time, it is important to consider possible conflicts of interest between those who live locally and those who participate remotely, since decisions primarily affect local residents.

According to the FG participants, several **key strategies help to overcome existing limitations**. First, focusing on local issues is highly effective because topics such as wastewater treatment, transport, logistics, and regional development are generally less politicized and easier for citizens to understand. Alongside this local focus, it is essential to provide training for both authorities and communities, ensuring that civil servants are just as educated as activists regarding the benefits of public participation. The participants also emphasized that showcasing successful cases is vital for motivating communities and building trust through tangible examples of change. Furthermore,

protecting participants by creating a safe environment for those who are active is necessary to encourage continued involvement. Finally, maintaining contact with Ukrainians abroad through community-diaspora interaction projects allows for a valuable exchange of experience, particularly in how those abroad have advocated for Ukraine's interests.

Conclusions

The evolution of democratic practice in Ukraine represents a sophisticated trajectory characterized by the struggle between post-Soviet institutional legacies and an increasingly assertive civic consciousness. Within the global context of a "crisis of democracy," where many established regimes face alienation, rising populism, and a decline in electoral participation, the Ukrainian case offers unique insights into how democratic innovations can fortify national resilience (Kiryukhin, 2023).

Our research on democratic innovations and citizen participation in decision-making in Ukraine, showed that despite the ongoing war, participation tools in Ukraine remain both accessible and important - especially in the absence of elections. They are not a substitute for elections, but one of the ways for citizens to be included in decision-making process and influence authorities.

Recommendations on improvement of effectiveness of these tools are based on understanding of the barriers and limitations they face during their implementation in Ukraine - socio-psychological and cultural, educational, institutional and procedural, infrastructural ones, and risk, distrust, and migrational challenges.

Socio-psychological and cultural barriers related to a dual-legacy mindset consisting of "small person syndrome" and Soviet-era paternalism, and also to loss of motivation when citizens become discouraged when efforts do not bring results. Educational barriers are about lack of awareness – citizens are often unaware of available participatory mechanisms or do not understand how they work. Institutional and procedural limitations are mostly about "imitation of participation" and legal constraints. Infrastructural challenges relate to physical and digital infrastructure. During the war, martial law and the destruction of physical infrastructure (schools, administrative buildings) limit the spaces where traditional, face-to-face deliberation can occur. A heavy shift toward "e-democracy" makes digital divide deeper and actualizes the risks of disengagement citizens with low digital literacy or those who lack trust in digital tools.

Speaking about personal risk challenges, in small settlements, a lack of anonymity leads to "fear of conflict." Also, in big settlements when the identity of the civil activist is known, expressing dissent may be perceived as a personal attack, leading to social condemnation or physical risk (e.g., the persecution of activists).

Distrust in government functions as both a barrier and, paradoxically, a motivator. While deep-seated distrust (rooted in corruption and historical repression) usually deters participation, "indignation" can drive engagement. Citizens may use participatory tools (like petitions) not out of faith in the system, but as a corrective measure to "show the authorities how things should be done."

Also, the migration challenge was mentioned. The war has introduced a unique limitation - territory-based fragmentation. Large-scale migration processes lead to the breakdown of social ties and the loss of the active core of communities. The massive displacement of Ukrainians (IDPs and refugees) creates a dilemma of representation. While online tools help maintain a connection with the diaspora, there is a potential "conflict of interest" between remote participants and local residents who must live with the physical consequences of decisions.

Table 2. Barriers and solutions to implementing democratic innovations in Ukraine.

Type of Barrier	Description	Mitigation Strategies
Socio-psychological and cultural	"Small person syndrome," Soviet-era paternalism, and loss of motivation when efforts yield only formal results without tangible implementation.	Tying participation to solving tangible local problems (transport, lighting, urban planning) to increase personal relevance. CSOs should lead advocacy campaigns to change negative perceptions and explain why participation matters for individuals.
Educational	Citizens are often unaware of available participatory mechanisms or do not understand how they work.	Implementing participatory schools and training, particularly for youth (e.g., student self-government). Sharing success stories is vital to demonstrate that individual voices can lead to real community change.
Institutional and procedural	"Imitation of participation" where processes end at signature collection; presence of heavy bureaucratic complexity and legal constraints.	Involving citizens in the monitoring of decisions, not just the initiation phase. Procedures must be simplified and freed of bureaucratic complexity to ensure they are accessible to the average citizen. Improve the regulatory framework.
Infrastructural	Destruction of physical infrastructure and a heavy, sometimes exclusive, shift toward "e-democracy."	Combining online and offline tools to ensure outreach to vulnerable groups (IDPs, veterans, people with disabilities). Information should be disseminated through multiple channels, including printed newsletters and in-person meetings.
Risk	Concerns regarding the personal safety and potential persecution of activists.	Creating a safe environment for active citizens. Protecting participants is essential to ensuring that engagement does not result in personal or professional harm.
Distrust in authorities	Low willingness to cooperate with officials due to corruption and historical repression.	Training for civil servants on the benefits of participation. Building trust by demonstrating impact ("the issue was resolved") and focusing on less politicized local topics like wastewater treatment or logistics.
Migrational	Large-scale migration leading to the breakdown of social ties and the loss of the active core of communities.	Maintaining contact with Ukrainians abroad through community-diaspora interaction projects. This allows for the reintegration of their international advocacy experience into local Ukrainian democratic processes.

Analysis of the data obtained allowed us to make list barriers for implementing democratic innovations in Ukraine and strategies to overcome them. Those strategies can be considered as recommendations for improvement of democratic innovation's effectiveness specific for Ukraine.

To make democratic innovations in Ukraine effective, the focus must shift from the formal existence of tools to their substantive utility. The strategies identified in the text emphasize closing the

loop between participation and results. By involving citizens in the monitoring of implementation and providing clear "success cases," the cycle of discouragement and paternalism can be broken.

Furthermore, the "human factor" is central to these solutions: educating both the youth and the authorities creates a shared language of cooperation. Addressing the digital divide through hybrid (online/offline) communication ensures that democratic progress does not exclude the most vulnerable or those in infrastructure-poor areas. Ultimately, by focusing on tangible local issues, democratic innovations become a practical necessity rather than an abstract concept, fostering a resilient and active civil society despite the challenges of war and migration.

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